

Rebuilding U.S. Governance:

Modeling a Progressive Federal Democratic Republic

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Executive Summary

In the current state of American politics, power has become unbalanced and largely unchecked, leading to the manipulation and marginalization of citizens. The influence held by the President is immense, and recent years have demonstrated how candidates' divisive ideologies can capitalize on and weaponize that. Nationwide, citizens face political movements that look to exploit polarization and erode democratic integrity. The top 10% of citizens hold 60% of the nation's wealth. Under the two-party system, citizens are divided and polarized, creating conditions that enable exploitative influence by the economic elite. The unbalanced concentration of power and wealth at this scale signals governance that has failed its people. While these flaws have attempted to undermine democracy, this model presents a government developed through a year of independent research—one that empowers its citizens, promotes a just society, and holds the nation's wealthiest accountable.

The proposed model is a progressive federal democratic republic that combines elements of cooperative federalism and transparent social democracy. By eliminating the President as a singular executive office, it offers a tiered and balanced Government between the federal Congress and governors, along with their local governments, with measures in place to promote public participation and accountability. It allows for state autonomy, while still being held within a shared federal system of direction. This model will decentralize power, secure social and economic equity, and build a voice for all citizens in government. From citizens to Congress, every level of government is responsible for upholding checks and balances, ensuring that citizens are no longer

unrepresented. The following section outlines the proposed government's framework and the redesigned role of Congress to address systemic weaknesses.

Government Design

The design centers around a re-imagined Congress and the elimination of the Presidency. With this change comes a redistribution of power, establishing a balanced system. Citizens will elect three congress members per state—one Democrat, one Republican, and one Independent—plus five representatives from the non-state regions of D.C., Puerto Rico, American Samoa, the Virgin Islands, and the Commonwealth of the Northern Mariana Islands. These 155 members will organize into five Federal Departments (31 members each), which will propose national policy standards and broad directives for the states, working with state officials to tailor goals to state needs and requiring a two-thirds vote of the governors to pass. There would also be quarterly cognitive testing for all elected officials seventy years and older, to ensure all representatives retain strong cognitive capacity. Terms will be for three years, and representatives will not serve more than two consecutive terms. This government operates under a top-down chain, with each level able to check and balance the others.

To develop the congressional departments, I drew inspiration from the seven Federal Departments of Switzerland, established in 1848 under their Constitution and subsequent amendments. Their departments aimed to be the supreme directional authority for the cantons (states), and according to studies between 2019 and 2023 by World Population Review, they boast an 82% citizen trust rating, the highest worldwide.

Congressional Departments

- **Department of Foreign Affairs**
 - Handle intercontinental relations
 - Trade and treaties
 - Global representation
 - Coordinate with intelligence for foreign analysis
 - Immigration

- **Department of Domestic Affairs, Education, and Health**
 - Manage state relations
 - Coordinate with intelligence for domestic analysis
 - Education funding, policy, and standards
 - Infrastructural oversight
 - Health policy
 - Medicare
 - Census and population registry

- **Department of Justice, Defence, & Civil Protection**
 - Federal court decision enforcement
 - Oversight for judicial impeachment
 - Federal law code management
 - Interstate police investigations
 - Homeland security and counterterrorism
 - Military policy oversight

- **Department of Finance & Economic Affairs**

- Creation and management of the federal budget
- State/County/City budget determination
- Collection and allocation of taxes
- Federal debt management
- Federal Reserve oversight
- Industry grants
- Corporate regulation and consumer protection
- **Department of Energy, Transport & Environmental Protection**
 - Energy grid management (and possible transitions)
 - Interstate roads, rails, and aviation policy
 - Climate and environmental protection
 - Natural resource management
 - FDA
 - Agriculture

Congressional Role

The departments will not operate entirely separately; together, Congress serves a larger role as the coordinator of the nation's governments. As stated previously, Congress will work with state officials to determine fair and attainable policy directives. These directives are designed to be broad, providing states with realistic goals, while not being overly restrictive for smaller states. The departments will also coordinate with one another to allocate resources and funding according to each state's specific needs. In contrast, states will determine how best to utilize these resources under their respective

departmental umbrella. Congress will also establish branch departments in each state, serving as separate entities, to coordinate between Congress and state officials and ensure effective development and balanced resource management. The concentration of national lawmaking authority within a single body is far too centralized, especially given the significant diversity in modern American society. Under this design, states are directed, not controlled, to find their place within national standards, and those regions will begin to express their individuality through policy.

Among these departments, Congress will manage the scope of foreign and domestic policy, ensuring that the country's government is working in the best interest of its people. In addition to their primary duties, an Emergency Response Council will be established in the event of a sudden war, pandemic, or disaster. The Council will select one person from each department, nominated by their peers, to act as a representative for their department and decide how to proceed in the given scenarios. All of Congress retains its voice, as members will advise and collaborate on decisions across their departments; however, all final decisions are made by the Council and must remain fully transparent. While Congress passes legislation with broad goals and standards for states to meet according to their abilities, the Emergency Council will apply them more strictly. It may modify existing standards due to the urgent crisis. The Council will rotate on a staggered schedule every six months, and Congress members may not serve more than once per three-year term. Transparency will be a cornerstone of the new government structure, ensuring the building of public trust in elected officials. This design will ensure national preparedness by anticipating crises rather than reacting to them as they occur.

Four independent federal agencies will operate outside of congressional jurisdiction and outside of political influence. NASA and the Postal Service will be funded by the federal government, but will continue to hire and plan separately, operating as they currently do. Though Congress will still cooperate with them, they will not manage them. The intelligence agencies will regularly report to the necessary departments, but again, Congress will not mediate their operations. These can continue to operate as they have in the past, funded through the government and acting as their own entities. Congress may help in modifying policy and goals, but there will be two-way communication to ensure fair representation. The agencies—NASA, the Postal Service, Intelligence, and Social Security—should benefit significantly from federal independence, and depoliticization might encourage them to make substantial progress.

State-Level Branches

While the departments will serve a directional role, Congress will implement branches in the states for execution. These branches will not operate as extensions of Congress but instead as state-managed coordination entities, working alongside the state to ensure effective development and resource management. Each branch will be overseen by the state, implementing federal programs locally to maintain national standards, while adapting to regional needs. Their primary function will be to distribute resources, contract labor through the state to meet directives, and provide direct assistance to cities and counties. With this, they will assist in creating state-level action plans that tailor federal directives to local needs.

Citizens require public services, and citizens need a government that will prioritize their provision on a national scale. These branches are designed to do just that: spread the influence of federal services to reach as many citizens as possible. Through improved environmental protection, energy and agriculture development, industry promotion, corporate regulation, health services, and immigration standards, state-level branches will push state societies forward.

Governors

With the elimination of the Presidency, each governor becomes the head executive of their state. Though their duties remain similar, Governors now carry substantially greater authority. It's designed to compare with the President's national powers, but focuses on the states. Governors will oversee statewide operations and collaborate with state officials and branches to secure the execution and direction of state-level programs. They will also be responsible for allocating federal funds to counties within budget minimums, as well as planning infrastructure alongside them, playing a key role in regional development.

As the President currently does, the governors should oversee in collaboration with Congress. They will play a crucial role in shaping national directives. They will hold quarterly "Governor Meetings" to discuss interstate relations, offer checks and balances to congressional legislation development, and have the power to recall members of Congress with a two-thirds vote. Within their states, governors will work to decide how to implement emergency council protocols in the event of a crisis. Again, they must

implement protocols and directives under the coordination of Congress, but Congress will pass broad goals for states to achieve as they are able.

To further mirror the current Presidential design, governors will have the power to veto and approve policies that county officials propose. However, this power is not absolute, as counties can overrule it with a 25% public petition. Within their states, citizens will participate in a vote every 4 years, and no Governor may serve more than two terms.

As this model changes the Governor's role to mirror that of the Presidency at the state level, cities and counties must also reorganize to guarantee fair policy application and public representation.

City and County Government

To organize the states in a way to remedy the damages done by gerrymandering, state officials will redraw county lines. The Department of Domestic Affairs, Education, and Health will design a broad standard, reducing the number of counties per state. Land will also be returned to native hands to further aid in this, widening their borders. With the increased funding and empowerment of county governments, communities will be consolidated and empowered. Their organization can remain the same, but they will have more responsibility over a larger area. County officials can propose legislation for their region to the governor for approval, and if it meets congressional standards, it will pass. If necessary, the state will provide funding and resources at the discretion of the governor. Under city and county budget and finance matters, such as taxes, bonds, and budget policy, the proposal will be put to a public vote by a simple majority.

City governments will also retain their current organization and propose ordinances to the mayor for approval. Mayors manage a city budget, and along with the approval of ordinances, manage it at the city's discretion. With the added benefits from the state-level branches, city governments will have far more influence, and public interest will increase. To aid in this, cities will fund and offer civic education in schools and for adults. City policies must align with county policies, and the two will work in cooperation to ensure balanced cohesion. For major infrastructural plans, cities and counties will propose to the governor for approval.

Government Coordination

As stated throughout this paper, this model elects Congress to serve a broad directional role. This role will require them to, of course, pass goal directives, but also oversee legislation passed within the states. Each representative will be empowered to coordinate with state officials and propose directive drafts interdepartmentally. These proposals could constitute a goal or change at the national scale or within a specific state, as needed. Nevertheless, this is not a policy mandate but rather a guide indicating the standards states will meet in any regard. Once proposed, debated, and defended, drafts are to be voted on interdepartmentally with a simple majority before moving to the congressional table. From there, it faces another debate and a simple majority vote before ultimately passing. Upon implementation, the department will oversee the application of this directive, and penalties, such as budget withholding or stricter directives, may be imposed if states fail to comply. To frame a possible alternative, departments can vote and pass directives autonomously, leaving major policy subject to

a full Congressional vote. The alternative is a very viable option; however, determining what constitutes a “major policy” will need strict guidelines.

Governors will serve as the head Executive figure among the states. They will approve state legislation, determine how to implement directives, and collaborate with state officials and departmental branches to ensure the effective implementation of policies. According to the previous Governors’ section of the paper, governors hold the power of veto; however, this power is not limited to just their respective states. Once Congress passes a directive, Governors may propose a veto to overturn it, requiring a two-thirds majority. In such cases, the Judicial Branch will review the veto’s validity or demand Congressional revision. Congressional representatives will either meet with governors when discussing a state-specific directive or request input from all governors through an online forum or the Governors' Meetings. These meetings will require mandatory attendance, ensuring fair treatment by Congress and cohesion among the states. They may result in collective recommendations to Congress or challenges to directives issued by Congress. Governors may also request assistance from Congress, ranging from budgetary disputes to emergency enforcement, with requests approved within the Departments. To encourage coordination, governors will submit quarterly feedback reports to the departments, which will include, but not be limited to, policy implementation updates, assistance requests, and directive complaints.

Within the states, and after county redistricting to amend gerrymandered lines, the scope of their operation may be the most critical aspect of this model. County officials will propose policy within their respective functions. Congress and the Governor will oversee proposed policy to guarantee that they’re both within Congressional direction and in the best interest of the people. To maintain a strong

national standard, governors may approve or veto legislation proposed by counties. Similarly, like Governors with Congress, counties will submit quarterly feedback reports to the Governors as a means to offer checks and balances, and county officials can hold a majority vote among counties to overrule a veto. Governors will manage and allocate any additional funding outside of a designated county budget. Still, if the proposed policy is to comply with Congressional goals, there will be a standard set for the budget. County officials will also draft laws for their people, within Congressional standards. Although, based on previous discussions, any law regarding taxes, bonds, budget policy, or significant infrastructural changes will require a public vote, and citizens will have a 5% petition rule to trigger a public vote on any policy. Differing legal systems between states will give regions individual identities and encourage people to engage actively in candidate research and political participation.

To hold all elected officials, congressional or state, accountable within the model, the state will enforce strict constraints for candidates. There must be specific qualifications held to be elected into office or hired to administer a government-related agency, either through related degrees or work experience. Currently, there are no educational or professional qualifications in place for departmental administrators. As long as you're a 25-year-old U.S. citizen within the state you serve, you can run as a congressional representative. The people should be governed by those who are the most qualified, not just those with the strongest connections.

Along with qualifications, there should be restrictions put in place for trading stocks. No elected official will be permitted to trade, promote, or advocate for trade within the market. If the state promotes a free market, then officials representing it should not be able to benefit from selective interference. There is also a current issue

with PAC funding, which gives corporations disproportionate influence in the political process. This model proposes a flexible cap system on the amount private corporations can donate to campaigns. This cap will differ depending on the state and position being campaigned for. The state will only permit donations during the campaign itself; once elected into office, all officials may receive no outside funding.

Voting

For congressional votes, the Electoral College will no longer be necessary. Each state will elect Congressional representatives to direct the country, not implement laws. Candidates for state government and Congress will provide reader-friendly brochures or informational papers detailing their goals, policy stances, and personal background to educate voters deeply during campaigns. Congressional votes will occur every 3 years, and candidates will not serve more than two consecutive terms. In the event of a tie, the candidates will be re-voted after two weeks, with a debate held each week. Mail-in ballots will be maintained and protected, and a 5% state petition may request a recount.

As mentioned before, policies regarding taxes, bonds, budget, environmental safety, and local development, proposed by cities and counties, will be put to a public vote. States should give people a strong voice in their communities, and in return, provide them with services to maintain it. The public will also vote on amendments to the national and state constitutions, as well as to existing legislation regarding the previous topics. Policy outside of this umbrella will be proposed and voted upon by Congress. Departments will draft legislation, then, with over 51% of a department's vote, they will propose it to the Congressional table. Once it passes a two-thirds vote, the

directive will take effect. Every individual will have a vote, and all departments will work cohesively. They will develop presentations for their proposals to inform Congress of what they've researched. A more cooperative and power-focused Congress will lead to stronger representation, and with the strength of local government, our communities will thrive.

With public votes, the state should begin the development of online voting. People will now be able to use their voice without having to attend council meetings or vote at polling booths. Within this system, the state could include information about its officials and current policies to ensure voter education. Online voting will, of course, require extensive cybersecurity protection before implementation and may necessitate the establishment of state branches dedicated to providing it. Until the state can ensure voter safety, states should use online voting only for in-state policy matters, not for elections. Voting reforms will empower citizens directly, and judicial reforms will ensure that constitutional operations remain impartial and just.

Supreme Court Alterations

Although the Supreme Court's powers can and should remain intact, this model will emphasize depoliticizing the environment. In appointing new Justices, each of the five departments appoints two, totaling ten, and this list is made public. Congress will then hold a vote on who should be appointed, with each member given one vote, and the nine justices with the most votes will be appointed. Justices will nominate their own alternatives for Congressional approval. If ever required, Congress may recall justices with a two-thirds vote and an additional majority judicial ballot.

The Courts will not serve term limits, and their alternatives will serve as advisors and mentees. They will also manage themselves, serving without political bias and without Congressional direction. Congress should have as little effect on the Courts as possible outside of nomination and recall, as political bodies should not govern judicial law.

Tax System

To provide its people with economic equity, the Government should consider these proposals for new tax structures.

Federal Income Tax Rates and State Income Tax Rates

\$0-\$10,000	10%
\$10,001-\$45,000	12%
\$45,001-\$100,000	14%
\$100,001-\$200,000	16%
\$200,001-\$250,000	18%
\$250,001-\$500,000	20%
\$500,001+	25%

\$0 to \$10,000.	0.5%
\$10,001 to \$25,000.	1%
\$25,001 to \$40,000.	2%
\$40,001 to \$55,000.	5%
\$55,001 to \$70,000.	6%
\$70,001 to \$350,000.	8%
\$350,001 to \$450,000	10%
\$450,001 to \$750,000.	11%
\$750,001-\$1,000,000	12%
\$1,000,001+	15%

Sales Tax- 0-5%

Under these rates, the aim is to maintain lower taxes for the majority of citizens and give states a basis to express their needs. For incomes of \$350,000 or more, states must apply the tax at a rate of 2% above the standard. For incomes lower than the stated

amounts, states may apply taxes as they deem necessary, with the numbers above serving as a base, up to a 2% deviation.

Corporate Marginal Tax Rates and Individual Marginal Tax Rates

\$0 – \$50,000	35%	\$0-\$50,000	0%
\$50,001 – \$100,000	40%	\$50,001 – \$100,000	10%
\$100,001 – \$250,000	42%	\$100,001 – \$250,000	20%
\$250,001 – \$1,000,000	45%	\$250,001 – \$1,000,000	30%
\$1,000,001 – \$10,000,000	50%	\$1,000,001 – \$10,000,000	35%
\$10,000,001-\$49,999,999	55%	\$10,000,001+	45%
\$50,000,000+	10%		

These rates aim to push for a more progressive economy. The corporate marginal tax only targets companies that make \$1,000,000 in revenue per year. It also features a base of 30% on all international corporate revenue. To promote in-state infrastructure, the state will apply a 10% tax reduction to revenue generated within the state. Additionally, the state will reduce taxes by 2% for every \$10 million invested back into the state's economy, with a cap of 10%. For companies seeking reinvestment reductions, they may permit Congress to monitor funding to projects within U.S. territories to guarantee a fair reward system. To give smaller companies a fair opportunity, there will be a 2% reduction for every 10% of profits reinvested in their state. Reinvestments could be through wage increases, local hiring, or community projects/investment. The rate for

revenue of \$50,000,000 and above will not be affected by these reductions, as it is already a lower rate than others. Along with this, Congress will need to issue regulations to prevent exploitation, as well as means to protect against tax evasion and avoidance.

For individual rates, a 2% reduction will be applied for every 10% of income earned in the U.S. These reductions will only be used for individual incomes exceeding \$100,000.

Marginal taxes will be collected and distributed by the Department of Finance & Economic Affairs. States will use these funds to support state programs, as well as the social programs outlined in the following section. Marginal taxes are the rates applied to the last dollar of the listed income, so if you make \$100,001, that one dollar will receive a 10% tax. Although the state may use this tax plan to strengthen existing programs, the model will propose funding additional support programs to benefit the people. These social market programs will be a cornerstone for economic equity under this government.

Social Market Programs

Using the revenue generated from this progressive tax plan, the states will manage social market programs. The states will provide housing, healthcare, grocery stores, and production factories. The states will employ workers for these programs locally, and will pay a livable wage, along with good benefits (Retirement plans, mental healthcare, dental & vision plans, and tuition reimbursement). Although Congress will direct the operation of these markets, the states will individually manage them.

To acquire houses for distribution, the government may buy them from corporations, purchase land and contract for development, and offer reductions for any

corporate assistance. These housing developments will be available for individuals working more than 30 hours per week, and will be designed as affordable, mid-sized units. To further develop solar batteries, states could utilize these developments by testing solar units in local neighborhoods. People will pay a fixed price for rent, power, and water. Congress will determine the rent price based on 30% of each state's median monthly salary. Rent should be around \$1,500 a month, and for a projected 1,000 sq. ft. unit, it represents an affordable standard for median-income households. The state will prioritize giving to citizens in the low- to middle-income brackets; however, to qualify for housing, you must work at least 30 hours a week. The state must provide aid to its citizens, but citizens must also provide for the state.

The state will also provide free healthcare for all citizens, now undeniably affordable under a more progressive tax system. Healthcare centers could be established across the country, whether in rural or urban areas, to provide all citizens with access to care. If the state cannot afford to provide universal care, it could still offer lower-level services, such as therapy, immunizations, vaccinations, basic treatments, and pharmaceuticals.

In 2023, 13.5% of U.S. households experienced food insecurity, meaning they lacked access to nutritious food. In 2024, the USDA found that 18% of households that held children were food insecure. Many citizens lack consistent access to nutritious and affordable food, which hinders their ability to maintain a productive lifestyle. Grocery chains are often free to exploit them and gouge prices. To tackle this, the model proposes the establishment of state-run grocery stores. The establishment of this market would not be a complete takeover; instead, the state may either construct and equip

grocery stores itself or purchase the buildings from previous owners. Corporations may also aid in the construction of these stores to receive tax reductions. Once the store is in place, the state will focus on hiring locally and ensuring a livable wage and fair benefits. Misfits Market, a grocery delivery service established in 2018, found that 40% of produce goes to waste yearly due to imperfections that corporations did not believe would sell. The state could follow this model, and source produce from local farms. The state will set prices as close to the market price as possible, within a standard set by Congress, and people will have complete access to affordable and organic groceries.

Along with housing, healthcare, and food, the government should also provide support for education. Congress can ensure that students receive quality education and provide reimbursement for undergraduate and possibly postgraduate degrees. Education should be universally accessible and attainable for all citizens who are willing to put in the effort.

Upwards of 770,000 citizens faced homelessness in 2024. To help address this crisis, the state will establish rehabilitation and aid clinics designed to provide housing, care, and preparation for work outside the clinic. The clinic will provide these services as long as the individual is responsive to support and will be at no expense. The clinic's focus will be on setting them up for success in society and helping them find a job that suits their skills and interests. Individuals may only be removed from care if the rehab proves successful, but they are unwilling to work.

The state will establish minimum goals for implementing these programs, and Congress will monitor states to ensure that programs are established and operating at a

high level. States will collaborate with Congress to determine these goals, as they should align with the state's capabilities, resources, and needs.

In future works, and as I go through my collegiate career, I plan to write detailed descriptions of the programs' projected costs, revenue, application, and possible methods of operation. I will apply these to papers and theses with more supportive literature to form a collective defense for the model.

Closing Statements

The dangers of concentrated power and wealth have historically proven to be very real. Radical political movements aim to divide people and lead them to believe that their voice will bring about change. Smaller regions are often left overlooked as Congress passes national policies, and state governments lack the necessary power to meet people's needs. But as Lincoln reminded the country in 1863, the U.S. is a government of the people, by the people, and for the people. This model encapsulates that idea by decentralizing power and empowering states to strengthen their communities, and holds corporations and wealthy elites accountable. It builds a fairer market, upholding economic equity and support. But most importantly, it ensures that every citizen has a voice, serving as the cornerstone of the nation.

This draft serves as the foundation for a model that I plan to refine and evolve throughout my research career. All feedback, critiques, and discourse will be welcome.

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